

Social

A STUDY OF SELF-CONCEPT IN RELATION TO ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AMONG 9TH STANDARD STUDENT

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Abstract

The specific needs for classifying these spectacles of self-concept in relation to academic achievement as a usual and predictable vital result of student growth and development rather than among compulsive symptom. The self-concept in relation to academic achievement turn out to be important in the actions of individuals. As the students are the stakes of the future generations their significance pattern of self-concept in relation to academic achievement are vital. So the present study intends to measure a study of self-concept in relation to academic achievement among 9th standard student. The investigator adopted survey method to study the self-concept between 9th standard students from selected government, private and aided school. For this study a sample of 220 students taken from five various schools which are situated in Coimbatore district selected by the investigator using simple random sampling technique.

Keywords: Self-Concept; Academic Achievement.

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1. Introduction

The main aim of education is the growth of physical, social activity, excitement, and knowledge of student sustainability. The sufficient education makes good excellence human resources for a quickly developing country. According to this reason, many countries have been demanding to develop the educational quality in the national policy and approach to enhance effective implementation. The student's academic achievement difficult is not only happening in India but it also in many countries around the world. Some countries have been taking research to solve this problem by instructive staff development, teaching methods, and parent and community cooperation and some country have been observing backward to student inner character by illustrating casual relationship manipulating to academic achievement.

Hence the investigator intends to assess the relationship between self-concept and academic achievement of 9th standard student.

1.1. Objectives of the Study

There are two main types of objectives undertaken by the investigator in this study work.

1.1.1. General Objectives

- To study on self-concept in relation to academic achievement among 9th standard students.
- To adopt questionnaire on self-concept scale among 9th standard students.

1.1.2. Specific Objectives

- To find out the self-concept among 9th standard school students.
- To find out the impact of personal variables like medium of instruction, gender, location of the school, type of school, educational qualification of father, educational qualification of mother, occupation of father, occupation of mother on self-concept among 9th standard school students.

2. Research Design

The investigator adopted survey method to study the self-concept among 9th standard students. For the study about self-concept, the sample size taken is 220 ninth standard students from five various schools which are situated in Coimbatore district.

Table 1: Distribution of Samples based on Variables

S.NO	Category	Subgroups	Number	%	Total
1.	Medium of Instruction	Tamil	91	41.4%	220
		English	129	58.6%	
2.	Gender	Male	128	58.2%	220
		Female	92	41.8%	
3.	Location of the School	Urban	111	50.5%	220
		Rural	109	49.5%	
4.	Type of School	Govt.	81	36.8%	220
		Aided	64	29.1%	
		Private	75	34.1%	
5.	Educational Qualification of father	Below 10 th	66	30%	220
		UG	71	32.3%	
		PG	23	10.5%	
		Professional	60	27.3%	
6.	Educational Qualification of mother	Below 10 th	41	18.6%	220
		UG	90	40.9%	
		PG	72	32.7%	

		Professional	17	7.7%	
7.	Occupation of father	Daily Wagers	53	24.1%	220
		Farmer	78	35.5%	
		Govt.Job	31	14.1%	
		Private	18	8.2%	
		Business	40	18.2%	
6.	Occupation of mother	Daily Wagers	24	10.9%	220
		Farmer	103	46.8%	
		Govt.Job	53	24.1%	
		Private	23	10.5%	
		Business	17	7.7%	

Table 2: Scoring of Each item

S.No	Dimension	Question no.	Scoring				
			SA	A	N	D	SD
1.	Self-Concept (for Positive Questions)	1 to 20, 25, 26, 28, 29	5	4	3	2	1
2.	Self-Concept (for Negative Questions)	21 to 24, 27	1	2	3	4	5

Table 3: Ranks assigned to the Self-Concept Scale

Self-Concept Scale	
Scores	Rank
29 to 67	Low
68 to 106	Moderate
107 to 145	High

Table 4: Ranks assigned to the Academic Achievement

Academic Achievement	
Scores	Rank
15 to 20	Low
21 to 25	Moderate
26 to 30	High

HYPOTHESIS 1:

There will be a significant mean score difference towards self-concept among 9th standard students with respect to medium of instruction

Table 5: Frequency and percentage difference towards self-concept among 9th standard students with respect to medium of instruction

Medium of Instruction	Low		Moderate		High		Total
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Tamil	0	0	23	25.27	68	74.72	91

English	3	2.32	25	19.38	101	78.29	129
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From the table 5 that amid the tamil medium students, 74.72% of them have high level of self-concept whereas 25.27% of them have moderate level of self-concept. Similarly, amid the English medium students, 78.29% of them have high level, 19.38% of them have moderate level and 2.32% of them have low level of self-concept.

Table 6: 't' values towards self-concept among 9th standard students with respect to medium of instruction

Medium of Instruction	Number	Mean	S.D	df	t value	p-value	Remarks
Tamil	91	3.15	0.64	220	0.63	0.26	Not significant
English	129	3.23	0.59				

(at 0.05 significant level the table value of 't' is 1.65)

From the table 6 the calculated value (0.63) is less than the table value of 't' (1.65), the null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference towards self-concept among 9th standard students with respect to medium of instruction.

HYPOTHESIS 2:

There will be a significant mean score difference towards academic achievement among 9th standard students with respect to medium of instruction

Table 7: Frequency and percentage difference towards academic achievement among 9th standard students with respect to medium of instruction

Medium of Instruction	Low		Moderate		High		Total
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Tamil	6	6.59	72	79.12	13	14.28	91
English	21	16.27	90	69.76	18	13.95	129

From the table 7 that amid the tamil medium students, 14.28% of them have high level whereas 79.12% of them have moderate level and 6.59% of them have low level of academic achievement. Similarly, amid the English medium students, 13.95% of them have high level, 69.76% of them have moderate level and 16.27% of them have low level of academic achievement.

HYPOTHESIS 3:

There will be a significant mean score difference towards self-concept among 9th standard students with respect to gender

Table 8: Frequency and percentage difference towards self-concept among 9th standard students with respect to gender

Gender	Low		Moderate		High		Total
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Male	0	0	32	25	96	75	128
Female	3	3.26	16	17.39	73	79.34	92

From the table 8 that amid the male students, 75% of them have high level whereas 25% of them have moderate level of self-concept. Amid the female students, 79.34% of them have high level, 17.39% of them have moderate level and 3.26% of them have low level of self-concept.

Table 9: 't' values towards self-concept among 9th standard students with respect to Gender

Gender	Number	Mean	S.D	df	t value	p-value	Remarks
Male	128	3.18	0.63	220	0.85	0.19	Not significant
Female	92	3.21	0.69				

(at 0.05 significant level the table value of 't' is 1.65)

From the table 9 the calculated value (0.85) is less than the table value of 't' (1.65), the null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference towards self-concept among 9th standard students with respect to gender.

HYPOTHESIS 4:

There will be a significant mean score difference towards academic achievement among 9th standard students with respect to gender

Table 10: Frequency and percentage difference towards academic achievement among 9th standard students with respect to gender

Gender	Low		Moderate		High		Total
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
Male	17	13.28	90	70.31	21	16.40	128
Female	10	10.86	72	78.26	10	10.86	92

From the table 10 that amid the male students, 16.40% of them have high level whereas 70.31% of them have moderate level, 13.28% of them have low level of academic achievement. Amid the female students, 10.86% of them have high level, 78.26% of them have moderate level and 10.86% of them have low level of academic achievement.

3. Conclusion

From the findings of the study conducted, it has been revealed that

- 1) There is no significant difference between medium of instruction towards self-concept among 9th standard students.
- 2) There is no significant difference between genders towards self-concept among 9th standard students.
- 3) There is no significant difference between localities towards self-concept among 9th standard students.
- 4) There is a significant difference among type of school towards self-concept among 9th standard students.
- 5) There is a significant difference among educational qualification of father towards self-concept among 9th standard students.
- 6) There is a significant difference among educational qualification of mother towards self-concept among 9th standard students.
- 7) There is a significant difference among occupation of father towards self-concept among 9th standard students.
- 8) There is a significant difference among occupation of mother towards self-concept among 9th standard students.

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